

EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES FOR MISTAKE CORRECTION IN EFL CLASSROOM

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Annotation: It is necessary to emphasize that sometimes it is rather complicated to give definite unequivocal advice whether to correct mistakes made by students practicing some language activities or not. This article is discussed effective strategies for mistake correction in EFL classroom.

Key words: mistake correction, language skills, speaking activities, self-esteem, educational process.

Some scientists consider that correction doesn't help the language learning process of internalizing rules, other scientists tend to be in favour of correcting all mistakes made by students as it seems more 'teacher-like' to do something about mistakes. Definitely there are cases in which constant interruption for mistake correction wouldn't be appropriate as well as situations in which it is better to aim at fluency rather than the accuracy.

It should be emphasized that the cases in which mistake correction is meaningless and inopportune are the following:

If we deal with weak students and they tend to make a lot of mistakes, firstly, it would be just impossible to correct all mistakes, moreover, it makes no sense since such students won't be able to continue speaking because they will definitely get flustered and lose train of thought due to ceaseless interruption, secondly, they wouldn't be able to perceive and remember all corrections, thus, they will surely continue to make the same mistakes in the future. On top of that students that are constantly interrupted for mistake correction can get frustrated, lose motivation,

develop psychological barrier that will hinder participation in class activities in the future.

It is inadvisable to interrupt speaking activity in case it is quite obvious for the teacher that the error made by the student is so called slip of the tongue error.

Teachers don't need to correct errors that are beyond students' current capabilities in English.

It is important to remember that there is no use trying to force weak or average students lacking speaking skills to talk, thereby provoking possible aggravation of the fear to make mistake and making them even less reluctant to speak in the future. It would be sensible to create amicable learning environment, where learners are not afraid of making mistakes and being ridiculed. The task of any foreign language teacher is to make students understand that mistakes made in the process of acquiring new language skills should be considered as an excellent opportunity to get knowledge or improve language skills.

Naturally, not all students are affected by the factors mentioned above. Basically, it is common for people with low self-esteem and high levels of anxiety, i.e. people experiencing psychological distress in all situations associated with the evaluation of their activities. [2] Since learning a foreign language is associated with a large number of errors (that is surely inevitable when learning new skills), participation in speaking activities becomes a major stress for students who are seeking to meet the expectations of others and are afraid to fail (i.e. to make a mistake speaking foreign language), which is a consequence of low self-esteem and self-doubt.

Unfortunately, these psychological characteristics are inherent to a large number of students, which means that the main task of the lesson will not be accomplished and such students will not acquire communication skills, learn to use foreign language for its intended purpose, i.e. as a means of communication. Taking into consideration all the above mentioned factors, it is important to help the teacher

find the necessary solutions so that the educational process might be carried out to the full extent, while minimizing stress factors arising in the process of foreign language communication.

In case we deal with shy students lacking confidence, improper correction could be quite embarrassing, thus leading to intimidation and wouldn't encourage such students to take active part in speaking activities next time. Moreover, if a student makes too many mistakes (be it grammar mistakes, vocabulary mistakes, pronunciation mistakes, etc.), constant interruption for correction would inevitably cause to lose the train of thought. What can be undertaken to avoid such unfavourable scenario?

One of the possible ways to give feedback on mistakes in a sensitive way is to jot down mistakes on note pads while listening to speaking activities and afterwards point out the mistakes to the student who made them or explain the rules to the whole class without giving unnecessary details of whose mistake it was. If such strategy of mistake correction is applied during the lesson, students feel free to make mistakes and it should be considered as a great advantage since it is well recognised fact that all we learn by making mistakes.

The task of a foreign language teacher is to create friendly homelike atmosphere in which mistakes made by students are not taken for "criminal acts" for which you are going to be undoubtedly punished, but as the advantageous integral part of any learning process without which it would be just impossible to acquire knowledge and new skills as well as to work on and improve existing ones. Students should be aware of the fact that to avoid situations in which you can definitely make a mistake would become the biggest mistake of all.

References:

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